

Acheiropoietos basilica, Thessaloniki

also known as “Church of the Virgin Mary Acheiropoietos, Thessaloniki”

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Entry tags: Religious Place, Christian Traditions, Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Greek Orthodox, City, Religious Group, Greece, Basilica

The church of the Acheiropoietos (meaning not made by hands in Greek), dedicated to the Mother of God is located to the south-eastern part of the city of Thessaloniki (Northern Greece). It was called thus because it housed a miraculous icon of the Virgin Mary Hodegetria. The church built in the third quarter of the 5th century is the oldest among those of the city of Thessaloniki still standing and it was constructed on a Roman public baths complex, parts of which are still visible underneath and around the building. The monument was repaired during the 7th century, after the earthquake of 620-630, while the other important phase of interventions dates to the late Byzantine period (14th-15th centuries). After the Ottoman conquest of Thessaloniki in 1430, the church was converted into a mosque, called “Eski Camii”. A minaret was added in the southwest corner. After the city’s liberation in 1912 it was again converted into a church and the minaret was demolished. Acheiropoietos is a three-aisled timber-roofed basilica with galleries above the two lateral aisles, measuring 51.90 m by 30.80 m. The side exterior walls are 14 m high, while the top of the roof of the central aisle lies at a height of 22 m. The building was initially larger, as indicated by the initial exonarthex to the west, the western gallery, the outer portico to the north and the skylight of the central aisle that do not survive today. The modern roof of the church, which is lower than the original was rebuilt. The central nave, which ends at the semi-circular sanctuary with the synthronon and the bishop’s throne, is divided from the lateral aisles by two marble colonnades. To the east side of the north aisle was added in the Middle Byzantine period the chapel of saint Irene. Traces of the staircase leading to the galleries are still preserved in the north-west corner of the basilica, while the annex of the south side is thought to have been the baptistery. The floors of the central, the south aisles and of the chapel of saint Irene are covered by slabs of marble from the time of the church. Part of the mosaics that have belonged to the earlier bath-house still survive beneath the floor of the north aisle. Fragments of the 5th-century mosaic decoration that includes crosses, geometric patterns, plants, fishes and birds, chalices and baskets are still preserved: i) in the colonnade intrados on the ground floor and south gallery; ii) in the narthex; and iii) in the window of the west wall. Their dating was based on the inscription on the intrados of the south and central arch of the tribelon that mentions the donor of the mosaics (and maybe also of the basilica), Andreas, identified as the priest who participated at the Council of Chalcedon of 451, representing the Archbishop of Thessaloniki. More recently it was suggested that Andreas was probably an Archbishop of Thessaloniki. The wall above the south colonnade is adorned with frescoes from the first decades of the 13th century. From the composition, which was depicting the Forty martyrs of Sebasteia, only eighteen of the figures have survived. They are represented either full-length or in bust wearing military uniform, each holding a cross. At either end of the row of martyrs was painted a candlestick with a lighted candle. Small traces of wall-paintings are also preserved in the chapel of saint Irene. The monolithic ambo, fragments of the mosaics and the sculptural decoration of Acheiropoietos basilica are exhibited at the Museum of Byzantine Culture of Thessaloniki.

Date Range: 450 CE - 1430 CE

Region: Thessaloniki, Greece

Region tags: Greece, Thessaloniki

Church of Acheiropoietos in Thessaloniki, Greece

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: De Bernardi Ferrero, D., "La Panagia Acheiropoietos di Salonicco", *Corsi di cultura sull'arte ravennate e bizantina* 22 (1975), 157-169.
- Source 2: Ευγγόπουλος, Α., "Περί την Αχειροποίητον Θεσσαλονίκης", *Μακεδονικά* 2 (1953), 472-487.
- Source 3: Raptis, K.T., *Αχειροποίητος Θεσσαλονίκης. Αρχιτεκτονική και γλυπτός διάκοσμος*, Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, 2016.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/acheiropoietos>
- Source 1 Description: Acheiropoietos church. Detailed description and photos
- Source 2 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=6970
- Source 2 Description: Description of Acheiropoietos church by the Ministry of Culture of Greece.
- Source 3 URL: http://www.ceti.gr/~akoutsou/3dicons/show.php?id=ARC3DICON3D_1ACH&res=UL&lang=
- Source 3 Description: 3d model and description of Acheiropoietos church

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Other [specify]: The basilica is not associated with a feature in the landscape.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: The church is a three-aisled basilica, with a chapel attached to the east side of the north aisle.

↳ One single feature

–Other [specify]: The monument is not composed by a single feature

↳ A group of structures:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: The basilica was though repaired during the 7th century, after the earthquake of 620-630, while the other important phase of interventions dates to the 14th-15th century. The timber roof is not the original.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: A chapel was added in the Middle Byzantine period.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The earthquakes of 620-630 damaged it but it was restored.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: The timber roof of the basilica is not the original. The church was also repaired after the 620-630 earthquake. It was also repaired in the 14th-15th centuries.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: The Mother of God, Virgin Mary.

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: We do not possess concrete evidence but most probably yes.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments and glass was used for the tesserae of the mosaics. Marble was used for the floor slabs and the sculpture of the basilica. Pigments and binders were used for the frescoes.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The depiction of eighteen of the Forty Martyrs of Sebasteia can be found on the wall above the south colonnade.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The depiction of eighteen of the Forty Martyrs of Sebasteia can be found on the wall above the south colonnade.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Birds and fishes were included in the mosaic decoration.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The abstract mosaic decoration of the church includes floral motifs, crosses, chalices, fishes and birds, while geometric patterns frame the areas. The mosaic floor has also geometric patterns.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The reliefs of the basilica are geometric or floral ornaments.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Like in the case of all Christian Orthodox churches, the basilica is furnished with an iconostasis on which are attached icons (panel paintings). Icons can be found also in other places of the basilica.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: The Forty Martyrs of Sebasteia are not worshipped specifically in the basilica. They belong to the list of saints of the Greek Orthodox Church.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Only fragments of the 13th-century frescoes are preserved.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The mosaics are Iconoclastic and therefore there is no figural

decoration.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: The mosaic inscription indicates the patron of the mosaics. The inscriptions of the frescoes indicate the martyr depicted.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc..]

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic inscription indicates the patron of the mosaics. The inscriptions of the frescoes indicate the martyr depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The inscriptions are informative for the persons visiting the basilica.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Like every Christian Orthodox church, Acheiropoietos contains an icon screen, as well as portable icons attached in different parts.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Humans (18 out of the 40 Martyrs of Sebasteia) were depicted only during the 13th-century in the monument. The mosaic decoration of the monument did not include figural decoration.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Birds and fishes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The aniconic mosaic decoration includes birds, fishes, chalices, plants and crosses.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: There are icons in the church, as well as the iconostasis found in all Christian Orthodox churches.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Only fragments of the 13th-century paintings is preserved in the church.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The mosaic decoration of the church is iconoclastic so there is no figural decoration

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: The mosaic inscription indicates the patron of the mosaics. The inscriptions of the frescoes indicate the martyr depicted.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The mosaic inscription indicates the patron of the mosaics. The inscriptions of the frescoes indicate the martyr depicted.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Survives the depiction of eighteen among the forty martyrs of Sebasteia.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses and chalices

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Survives the depiction of eighteen among the forty martyrs of Sebasteia.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Only fragments of the mosaic and fresco decoration of the church survive.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Yet, faithful and pilgrims pray to God, the Mother of God and the Saints at this place.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Yet, faithful and pilgrims pray to Saints at this place.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Via prayer.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Material offerings can vary from very expensive objects to food such as olive oil, wine and bread used for the liturgy.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The basilica was repaired in the 7th century and in the 14th-15th centuries.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: The Ephorate of Antiquities of Thessaloniki in collaboration with the Archbishopric of Thessaloniki are responsible for the preservation and maintenance of the building.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The basilica is one of the most important early Christian monuments, so it is maintained and guarded by a team of experts from different fields.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: The church is not a site of pilgrimage. Yet, faithful were/are visiting the basilica for praying.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: Services and liturgy are taking place in the church.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Services and liturgy are taking place in the church.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: It is impossible to provide an estimation.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: The services are taking place following the liturgical cycle of the Greek Orthodox Church.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The various Christian services and the Holy Liturgy are synchronic practices.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

Notes: They are present at the church for the services and liturgies, as well as for supporting the faithful in their spiritual quest.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian Orthodox clergy is organised hierarchically.

Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: It is under the jurisdiction of the Archbishopric of Thessaloniki. The monument is maintained by a team of experts including archaeologists, engineers etc.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: In the church are definitely preserved records and documents relevant to its history. It is unknown though from which period date the oldest ones.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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